

Effectiveness of Structured teaching Programme on Knowledge and Practices regarding Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Malnutrition among under-five children remains a major public health concern, especially in low- and middle-income countries. The concept of the Rainbow Nutrition Package, which promotes the consumption of diverse coloured fruits and vegetables, plays a significant role in improving nutritional status. However, inadequate knowledge and poor dietary practices among mothers contribute to persistent malnutrition.

AIM:

To evaluate the effectiveness of a structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding the Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under-five children residing in selected urban areas.

METHODS:

A quantitative research approach with a pre-experimental one-group pretest–posttest design was adopted. A total of 100 mothers of under-five children were selected using non-probability convenient sampling from selected urban areas. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and observation checklist. The intervention consisted of a structured teaching programme on Rainbow Nutrition Package. Post-test assessment was conducted after 7 days. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including paired t-test and Fisher's exact test.

RESULTS:

The findings revealed a significant improvement in knowledge and practices following the intervention. The mean knowledge score increased from 5.1 (pretest) to 13.6 (posttest) ($t = 24.3, p < 0.05$). Similarly, the mean practice score improved from 3.4 to 8.7 ($t = 30.2, p < 0.05$). In the pretest, 64% of participants had poor knowledge, whereas post-intervention, 100% demonstrated good knowledge. Practices also improved markedly, with 98% showing good practices in the posttest. A significant association was found between knowledge and annual income ($p < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION:

The structured teaching programme was highly effective in enhancing knowledge and practices regarding the Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under-five children. Educational interventions can play a crucial role in improving child nutrition and preventing malnutrition at the community level.

KEYWORDS:

Structured teaching programme; Rainbow Nutrition Package; mothers; under-five children; knowledge; practices; community health nursing.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of eating the rainbow of healthful foods would seem to be an effective strategy for assisting people in improving their diet. It can be implemented by all ages through a variety of methods. For easy reference and remembering, the importance of getting each colour may be associated with some general related health benefit seat the rainbow nutrition is about eating many fruits and vegetables of many different colors every day, which offers different nutrients to the body.

In a world where nutrition and well-being have become paramount concerns in the recent years, the concept of "eating a rainbow" has emerged as a captivating and practical approach to achieving a balanced and healthy diet. The idea behind eating a rainbow is simple yet powerful: consuming a variety of fruits and vegetables that span the entire spectrum of colors', much like the colour' s of a rainbow. The vibrant colors of these foods not only appeal to our senses but also indicate the presence of various phytochemicals, vitamins, minerals and antioxidants

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The attainment of good nutrition depends on and encompasses the entire food supply. Plant and animal foods and their various components are the primary vehicles that provide nourishment to human beings. Nutrition is vital, not only in the growth and development of humans and animals but also in the prevention and treatment of disease. Nutrition is also fundamental to the maintenance of good health and functionality. Basic and applied research on the interrelations between nutrition and noncommunicable diseases, nutrient composition, and nutrition monitoring represents the underpinnings for healthy populations and robust economies. Thus, innovative nutrition research and education provide the basis for solutions to larger health-related issues, allowing individuals to live healthier, more productive lives. The importance of nutrition, as an integral part of the solution to many societal, environmental, and economic challenges facing the world, has just started to be fully appreciated.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Children need the right foods at the right time to grow and develop to their full potential. The most critical time for good nutrition is during the 1,000-day period from pregnancy until a child's second birthday.⁶

In the first two years of life, breastfeeding saves lives, shields children from disease, boosts brain development and guarantees children a safe and nutritious food source. UNICEF and the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend that infants begin breastfeeding within one hour of birth, be exclusively breastfed for the first six months, and continue breastfeeding until 2 years of age or beyond.

The rainbow diet is not a new idea, but it's newly popular. The idea behind it is that colorful vegetables and fruit contain specific micronutrients that support our health and combat biological stress with antioxidants and anti-inflammatory molecules. This type of biological stress affects our body at a cellular level probably know it as "oxidative stress", which is caused by free radicals. Fortunately, the antioxidants in rainbow diet foods help the body to neutralize free radicals and stop them from damaging your cells. Free radicals are generated by metabolism (the sum of life-giving chemical reactions inside your cells) and our environment. Here are some common sources of free radicals in everyday life

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a quantitative research approach in the present study. The research design that is chosen for this study is a Pre-experimental one group pre test post test group design. The population was mothers under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city. The sample consisted of 100 residing in a selected mothers under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city. The sampling technique used was the non-probability convenient sampling technique. The setting was a selected urban areas of the city. The tool was Structured questionnaire and observation checklist to assess the pre-existing level of knowledge and practices regarding rainbow nutrition package among mothers under five children. The structured teaching programme given to the selected samples about rainbow nutrition package. In this study, eating many fruits and vegetables of many different colours every day, which offers different nutrients to the body.

The list of experts was 7 from Community Health Nursing. 1 from a statistician, 2 from community medicine, 2 from a nutritionist, 1 child health nursing. The content validity of the tool was done and was found to be 0.97. For the pilot study sample of 10 mothers under five children the researcher approached the participants individually and discussed the objectives of the study and written consent was obtained for the participation in the study. Intervention (structured teaching programme on rainbow nutrition package) was given to the participants. The main study was done for 28 days. Structured teaching programme was given to the participants. Post test will conducted after of 7 days gap of intervention to assess the knowledge and practices of structured teaching programme on rainbow nutrition package. The analysis of the study was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. The master sheet was prepared. The data was presented in the form of tables, graphs and charts. Statistics were performed with the help of paired t-tests, and Fisher's exact test.

RESULT

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

1.AGE:-The percentage-wise distribution of respondents according to their age reveals that Age group 21% of the mothers of under five children had age upto 20 years, 37% of them had age 21-25 years, 31% of them had age 26-30 years and 11% of them had age 31-35 years.

1.2EDUCATION:-In this group shows 7% of them were illiterate, 31% of them had primary education, 42% of them had secondary education and 20% of them had graduation and above. This indicates that the majority of respondents had attained secondary education, with fewer individuals having lower educational qualifications.

1.3RELIGION:-In this group picture shows 16% of them were Christian, 48% of them were Hindu, 8% of them were Muslim and 28% of them had other religion. This result shows that in percentages of Hindu religious

1.4 OCCUPATION :-In this group occupation of mothers shows 22% of them had daily wages, 24% of them were housewives, 34% of them were private employees and 20% of them were self-employed. In this result shows high percentage is private employees.

1.5 ANNUAL INCOME:-In this diagram shows Annual income of family 2% of them had income Rs.10000-20000, 15% of them had income Rs.20000-30000 and 83% of them had income above Rs. 30000. This indicates that the majority of respondents had attained more income of family in experiment group is above Rs.30.000 and above

1.6 NO OF CHILDREN UNDER 5 YEAR:-In this group 43% of them had one child under five years, 36% of them had two under five children and 21% of them had more than 2 under five children. The result show high percentage of 43% mothers having one children under 5 year

1.7 TYPE OF FAMILY :-In this group picture shows 17% of them had extended family, 32% of them had joint family and 51% of them had nuclear family. In this graph show high percentage of nuclear type of family

1.8 TYPE OF DIET:- In this group diagram Shows 63% of them were non vegetarians and 37% of them were vegetarians. This indicates that non veg diet habit of family were more prevalent among the respondents, with a smaller proportion following a vegetarian diet.

1.9 MEAL PATTERN FOLLOWED AT HOME:- In this picture shows 17% of them had two meals in the day, 54% of them had three meals, 21% of them had four meals and 8% of them had 5 meals. In this result show that meal pattern followed at home 3 meal pattern more than other

Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas

n=100

Knowledge	Pretest		Posttest	
	Frequency	percentage	Frequency	percentage
Poor	64	64%	0	0%
Average	26	26%	0	0%
Good	10	10%	100	100%

Fig4.12 A bar diagram pre -test and post-test pre-existing level of knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition package among mothers under five children

In pretest, 64% of the mothers of under five children had poor knowledge, 26% of them had average knowledge and 10% of them had good knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition package. In posttest, all of them had good knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition package. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition Package among mothers of under five children.

Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on practices regarding rainbow nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas

n=100

Practices	Pretest		Posttest	
	Frequency	percentage	Frequency	percentage
Poor	55	55%	0	0%
Average	45	45%	2	2%
Good	0	0%	98	98%

Fig4.14 Practices regarding regarding rainbow nutrion packages among mothers of under five children residinf selected urban areas in pretest and posttest

In pretest, 55% of the mothers of under five children had poor practices and 45% of them had average practices regarding rainbow nutrition package. In posttest, 2% of the mothers of under five children had average practices and 98% of them had good practices regarding rainbow nutrition package. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the practices regarding rainbow nutrition Package among mothers of under five children.

Table 4.18 : Fisher's exact test for the association of knowledge regarding rainbow nutrition Package among mothers of under five children with their demographic variables n=100

Sr.no	Demographic variable		Knowledge			p-value
			Poor	Average	Good	
1.	Age	Upto 20 years	14	3	4	0.358
		21-25 years	22	12	3	
		26 – 30 years	22	8	1	
		31-35 years	6	3	2	
2.	Education	Illiterate	4	2	1	0.895
		Primary	20	7	4	
		Secondary	28	10	4	
		Graduation and above	12	7	1	
3.	Religion	Christian	13	3	0	0.739
		Hindu	29	14	5	
		Muslim	5	2	1	
		Others	17	7	4	
4.	Occupation	Daily wages	16	5	1	0.247
		House wife	12	6	6	
		Private employees	23	10	1	
		Self employed	13	5	2	
5.	Annual income	Rs.10,000- Rs.20,000	1	1	0	0.010
		Rs.20,000- Rs.30,000	15	0	0	
		Rs.30,000 and above	48	25	10	
6.	Number of children under 5 years	One	27	11	5	0.758
		Two	21	11	4	
		More than 2	16	4	1	
7.	Type of family	Extended	9	5	3	0.554
		Joint	21	7	4	
		Nuclear	34	14	3	
8.	Type of diet	Non-veg	40	15	8	0.515
		veg	24	11	2	
9.	Meal pattern followed at home	2 meals	8	7	2	0.297
		3 meals	33	15	6	
		4 meals	15	4	2	
		5 meals	8	0	0	

Results shows Since the p-value corresponding to family income was small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable annual income was found to have significant association with the knowledge among mothers of under five children regarding rainbow nutrition Package.

DISCUSSION

The discussion concludes the research report. A thoughtful discussion section clarifies the meaning of the research findings. The most crucial component of every study report is this one. The results of the current study have been described in relation to the research problem's aim, and the researcher has also discussed the study's findings in relation to the outcome objective. The present study was conducted to assess the Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city. A review of literature was done and sample size, study design, etc. were determined. The study approach used was the quantitative approach, the study design used was pre experimental one group pre-test post test design. The population included was mothers under five children and the accessible population included all mothers of under five age children residing in selected urban areas residing in selected areas. A total of 100 samples were selected using the non-probability convenient sampling technique; The tool was selected for the collection of data. Structured questionnaire was used to assess the level of knowledge and practices regarding rainbow nutrition package.

CONCLUSION

The chapter present the conclusion drawn, implications, limitation and recommendation the focus of this study was to assess Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city.

The aim of the study was to assess the Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding Rainbow Nutrition Package among mothers of under five children residing in selected urban areas of the city.

The study made use of pre-experimental design. The study population consisted residing in selected urban areas of the city. A total of 100 samples were taken with a non-probability convenient sampling technique. For generating necessary data, Content validation was done by 13 experts from different fields. At the start of the data collection, the study was discussed with samples. Samples were selected according to the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. Explained the purpose of the study and assured about the confidentiality of the information between the investigator and the respondent. Before Data Collection consent was taken from the mothers under five children. Data was collected from 100 samples from residing in selected urban areas of the city. Findings were recorded according to the tool. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics. The Fisher's exact test was used to find the association of study finding with selected demographic variables..

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